

Article

Neutrosophic Quadruple BCK/BCI -Algebras

Young Bae Jun ¹, Seok-Zun Song ^{2,*}

¹ Department of Mathematics Education, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju 52828, Korea; skywine@gmail.com

² Department of Mathematics, Jeju National University, Jeju 63243, Korea

³ Mathematics & Science Department, University of New Mexico, 705 Gurley Ave., Gallup, NM 87301, USA; fsmarandache@gmail.com

⁴ Department of Mathematics, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran 1983963113, Iran; bordbar.amirh@gmail.com

* Correspondence: szsong@jejunu.ac.kr

Received: 20 April 2018; Accepted: 18 May 2018; Published: 18 June 2018

Abstract: The notion of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -number is considered, and a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -algebra, which consists of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -numbers, is constructed. Several properties are investigated, and a (positive implicative) ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra and a closed ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCI -algebra are studied. Given subsets A and B of a BCK/BCI -algebra, the set $NQ(A, B)$, which consists of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -numbers with a condition, is established. Conditions for the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (positive implicative) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra are provided, and conditions for the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (closed) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI -algebra are given. An example to show that the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is not a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra is provided, and conditions for the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ to be a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra are then discussed.

Keywords: neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -number; neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -algebra; neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra; (positive implicative) neutrosophic quadruple ideal

MSC: 06F35; 03G25; 08A72

1. Introduction

The notion of a neutrosophic set was developed by Smarandache [1–3] and is a more general platform that extends the notions of classic sets, (intuitionistic) fuzzy sets, and interval valued (intuitionistic) fuzzy sets. Neutrosophic set theory is applied to a different field (see [4–8]). Neutrosophic algebraic structures in BCK/BCI -algebras are discussed in [9–16]. Neutrosophic quadruple algebraic structures and hyperstructures are discussed in [17,18].

In this paper, we will use neutrosophic quadruple numbers based on a set and construct neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -algebras. We investigate several properties and consider ideals and positive implicative ideals in neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra, and closed ideals in neutrosophic quadruple BCI -algebra. Given subsets A and B of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -algebra, we consider sets $NQ(A, B)$, which consist of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI -numbers with a condition. We provide conditions for the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (positive implicative) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra and for the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (closed) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI -algebra. We give an example to show that the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is not a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra, and we then consider conditions for the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ to be a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK -algebra.

2. Preliminaries

A BCK/BCI-algebra is an important class of logical algebras introduced by Iséki (see [19,20]).

By a BCI-algebra, we mean a set X with a special element 0 and a binary operation $*$ that satisfies the following conditions:

- (I) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) (((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0)$;
- (II) $(\forall x, y \in X) ((x * (x * y)) * y = 0)$;
- (III) $(\forall x \in X) (x * x = 0)$;
- (IV) $(\forall x, y \in X) (x * y = 0, y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y)$.

If a BCI-algebra X satisfies the identity

- (V) $(\forall x \in X) (0 * x = 0)$,

then X is called a BCK-algebra. Any BCK/BCI-algebra X satisfies the following conditions:

$$(\forall x \in X) (x * 0 = x) \tag{1}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) (x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x) \tag{2}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * y) * z = (x * z) * y) \tag{3}$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y) \tag{4}$$

where $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. Any BCI-algebra X satisfies the following conditions (see [21]):

$$(\forall x, y \in X) (x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y), \tag{5}$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X) (0 * (x * y) = (0 * x) * (0 * y)). \tag{6}$$

A BCK-algebra X is said to be *positive implicative* if the following assertion is valid.

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y) * z). \tag{7}$$

A nonempty subset S of a BCK/BCI-algebra X is called a *subalgebra* of X if $x * y \in S$ for all $x, y \in S$. A subset I of a BCK/BCI-algebra X is called an *ideal* of X if it satisfies

$$0 \in I, \tag{8}$$

$$(\forall x \in X) (\forall y \in I) (x * y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I). \tag{9}$$

A subset I of a BCI-algebra X is called a *closed ideal* (see [21]) of X if it is an ideal of X which satisfies

$$(\forall x \in X) (x \in I \Rightarrow 0 * x \in I). \tag{10}$$

A subset I of a BCK-algebra X is called a *positive implicative ideal* (see [22]) of X if it satisfies (8) and

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X) (((x * y) * z \in I, y * z \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I). \tag{11}$$

Observe that every positive implicative ideal is an ideal, but the converse is not true (see [22]). Note also that a BCK-algebra X is positive implicative if and only if every ideal of X is positive implicative (see [22]).

We refer the reader to the books [21,22] for further information regarding BCK/BCI-algebras, and to the site "<http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/neutrosophy.htm>" for further information regarding neutrosophic set theory.

3. Neutrosophic Quadruple BCK/BCI-Algebras

We consider neutrosophic quadruple numbers based on a set instead of real or complex numbers.

Definition 1. Let X be a set. A neutrosophic quadruple X -number is an ordered quadruple (a, xT, yI, zF) where $a, x, y, z \in X$ and T, I, F have their usual neutrosophic logic meanings.

The set of all neutrosophic quadruple X -numbers is denoted by $NQ(X)$, that is,

$$NQ(X) := \{(a, xT, yI, zF) \mid a, x, y, z \in X\},$$

and it is called the *neutrosophic quadruple set* based on X . If X is a BCK/BCI-algebra, a neutrosophic quadruple X -number is called a *neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number* and we say that $NQ(X)$ is the *neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-set*.

Let X be a BCK/BCI-algebra. We define a binary operation \odot on $NQ(X)$ by

$$(a, xT, yI, zF) \odot (b, uT, vI, wF) = (a * b, (x * u)T, (y * v)I, (z * w)F)$$

for all $(a, xT, yI, zF), (b, uT, vI, wF) \in NQ(X)$. Given $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 \in X$, the neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number (a_1, a_2T, a_3I, a_4F) is denoted by \tilde{a} , that is,

$$\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2T, a_3I, a_4F),$$

and the zero neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number $(0, 0T, 0I, 0F)$ is denoted by $\tilde{0}$, that is,

$$\tilde{0} = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F).$$

We define an order relation " \ll " and the equality " $=$ " on $NQ(X)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y} &\Leftrightarrow x_i \leq y_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \\ \tilde{x} = \tilde{y} &\Leftrightarrow x_i = y_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(X)$. It is easy to verify that " \ll " is an equivalence relation on $NQ(X)$.

Theorem 1. If X is a BCK/BCI-algebra, then $(NQ(X); \odot, \tilde{0})$ is a BCK/BCI-algebra.

Proof. Let X be a BCI-algebra. For any $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) &= (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \\ &\quad \odot (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \\ &= ((x_1 * y_1) * (x_1 * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * (x_2 * z_2))T, \\ &\quad ((x_3 * y_3) * (x_3 * z_3))I, ((x_4 * y_4) * (x_4 * z_4))T) \\ &\ll (z_1 * y_1, (z_2 * y_2)T, (z_3 * y_3)I, (z_4 * y_4)F) \\ &= \tilde{z} \odot \tilde{y} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \odot (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \\ &= (x_1 * (x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * (x_2 * y_2))T, (x_3 * (x_3 * y_3))I, (x_4 * (x_4 * y_4))F) \\ &\ll (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \\ &= \tilde{y} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \odot \tilde{x} &= (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \odot (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \\ &= (x_1 * x_1, (x_2 * x_2)T, (x_3 * x_3)I, (x_4 * x_4)F) \\ &= (0, 0T, 0I, 0F) = \tilde{0}. \end{aligned}$$

Assume that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x} = \tilde{0}$. Then

$$(x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F)$$

and

$$(y_1 * x_1, (y_2 * x_2)T, (y_3 * x_3)I, (y_4 * x_4)F) = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F).$$

It follows that $x_1 * y_1 = 0 = y_1 * x_1$, $x_2 * y_2 = 0 = y_2 * x_2$, $x_3 * y_3 = 0 = y_3 * x_3$ and $x_4 * y_4 = 0 = y_4 * x_4$. Hence, $x_1 = y_1$, $x_2 = y_2$, $x_3 = y_3$, and $x_4 = y_4$, which implies that

$$\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) = \tilde{y}.$$

Therefore, we know that $(NQ(X); \odot, \tilde{0})$ is a BCI-algebra. We call it the *neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra*. Moreover, if X is a BCK-algebra, then we have

$$\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{x} = (0 * x_1, (0 * x_2)T, (0 * x_3)I, (0 * x_4)F) = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F) = \tilde{0}.$$

Hence, $(NQ(X); \odot, \tilde{0})$ is a BCK-algebra. We call it the *neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra*. □

Example 1. If $X = \{0, a\}$, then the neutrosophic quadruple set $NQ(X)$ is given as follows:

$$NQ(X) = \{\tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \tilde{3}, \tilde{4}, \tilde{5}, \tilde{6}, \tilde{7}, \tilde{8}, \tilde{9}, \tilde{10}, \tilde{11}, \tilde{12}, \tilde{13}, \tilde{14}, \tilde{15}\}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{0} &= (0, 0T, 0I, 0F), \tilde{1} = (0, 0T, 0I, aF), \tilde{2} = (0, 0T, aI, 0F), \tilde{3} = (0, 0T, aI, aF), \\ \tilde{4} &= (0, aT, 0I, 0F), \tilde{5} = (0, aT, 0I, aF), \tilde{6} = (0, aT, aI, 0F), \tilde{7} = (0, aT, aI, aF), \\ \tilde{8} &= (a, 0T, 0I, 0F), \tilde{9} = (a, 0T, 0I, aF), \tilde{10} = (a, 0T, aI, 0F), \tilde{11} = (a, 0T, aI, aF), \\ \tilde{12} &= (a, aT, 0I, 0F), \tilde{13} = (a, aT, 0I, aF), \tilde{14} = (a, aT, aI, 0F), \text{ and } \tilde{15} = (a, aT, aI, aF). \end{aligned}$$

Consider a BCK-algebra $X = \{0, a\}$ with the binary operation $*$, which is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Cayley table for the binary operation “*”.

*	0	a
0	0	0
a	a	0

Then $(NQ(X), \odot, \tilde{0})$ is a BCK-algebra in which the operation \odot is given by Table 2.

Table 2. Cayley table for the binary operation “ \odot ”.

\odot	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{15}$
$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$

Table 2. Cont.

\odot	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{15}$
$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{0}$	$\tilde{0}$
$\tilde{15}$	$\tilde{15}$	$\tilde{14}$	$\tilde{13}$	$\tilde{12}$	$\tilde{11}$	$\tilde{10}$	$\tilde{9}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{6}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{2}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{0}$

Theorem 2. The neutrosophic quadruple set $NQ(X)$ based on a positive implicative BCK-algebra X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra.

Proof. Let X be a positive implicative BCK-algebra. Then X is a BCK-algebra, so $(NQ(X); \odot, \tilde{0})$ is a BCK-algebra by Theorem 1. Let $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)$. Then

$$(x_i * z_i) * (y_i * z_i) = (x_i * y_i) * z_i$$

for all $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ since $x_i, y_i, z_i \in X$ and X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra. Hence, $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} * \tilde{z}) = (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}$; therefore, $NQ(X)$ based on a positive implicative BCK-algebra X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra. \square

Proposition 1. The neutrosophic quadruple set $NQ(X)$ based on a positive implicative BCK-algebra X satisfies the following assertions.

$$(\forall \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)) (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{z} \Rightarrow \tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} \ll \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z}) \tag{12}$$

$$(\forall \tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(X)) (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{y} \Rightarrow \tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y}). \tag{13}$$

Proof. Let $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)$. If $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{z}$, then

$$\tilde{0} = (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} = (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z}),$$

so $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} \ll \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z}$. Assume that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{y}$. Using Equation (12) implies that

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{0},$$

so $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}$, i.e., $\tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y}$. \square

Let X be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Given $a, b \in X$ and subsets A and B of X , consider the sets

$$NQ(a, B) := \{(a, aT, yI, zF) \in NQ(X) \mid y, z \in B\}$$

$$NQ(A, b) := \{(a, xT, bI, bF) \in NQ(X) \mid a, x \in A\}$$

$$NQ(A, B) := \{(a, xT, yI, zF) \in NQ(X) \mid a, x \in A; y, z \in B\}$$

$$NQ(A^*, B) := \bigcup_{a \in A} NQ(a, B)$$

$$NQ(A, B^*) := \bigcup_{b \in B} NQ(A, b)$$

and

$$NQ(A \cup B) := NQ(A, 0) \cup NQ(0, B).$$

The set $NQ(A, A)$ is denoted by $NQ(A)$.

Proposition 2. Let X be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Given $a, b \in X$ and subsets A and B of X , we have

- (1) $NQ(A^*, B)$ and $NQ(A, B^*)$ are subsets of $NQ(A, B)$.
- (1) If $0 \in A \cap B$ then $NQ(A \cup B)$ is a subset of $NQ(A, B)$.

Proof. Straightforward. \square

Let X be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Given $a, b \in X$ and subalgebras A and B of X , $NQ(a, B)$ and $NQ(A, b)$ may not be subalgebras of $NQ(X)$ since

$$(a, aT, x_3I, x_4F) \odot (a, aT, u_3I, v_4F) = (0, 0T, (x_3 * u_3)I, (x_4 * v_4)F) \notin NQ(a, B)$$

and

$$(x_1, x_2T, bI, bF) \odot (u_1, u_2T, bI, bF) = (x_1 * u_1, (x_2 * u_2)T, 0I, 0F) \notin NQ(A, b)$$

for $(a, aT, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(a, B)$, $(a, aT, u_3I, v_4F) \in NQ(a, B)$, $(x_1, x_2T, bI, bF) \in NQ(A, b)$, and $(u_1, u_2T, bI, bF) \in NQ(A, b)$.

Theorem 3. If A and B are subalgebras of a BCK/BCI-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a subalgebra of $NQ(X)$, which is called a neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra.

Proof. Assume that A and B are subalgebras of a BCK/BCI-algebra X . Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$ and $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(A, B)$. Then $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in A$ and $x_3, x_4, y_3, y_4 \in B$, which implies that $x_1 * y_1 \in A$, $x_2 * y_2 \in A$, $x_3 * y_3 \in B$, and $x_4 * y_4 \in B$. Hence,

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $NQ(A, B)$ is a subalgebra of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 4. If A and B are ideals of a BCK/BCI-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$, which is called a neutrosophic quadruple ideal.

Proof. Assume that A and B are ideals of a BCK/BCI-algebra X . Obviously, $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$ and $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $x_1 * y_1 \in A$, $x_2 * y_2 \in A$, $x_3 * y_3 \in B$ and $x_4 * y_4 \in B$. Since $\tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$, we have $y_1, y_2 \in A$ and $y_3, y_4 \in B$. Since A and B are ideals of X , it follows that $x_1, x_2 \in A$ and $x_3, x_4 \in B$. Hence, $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A, B)$, so $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Since every ideal is a subalgebra in a BCK-algebra, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 1. If A and B are ideals of a BCK-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a subalgebra of $NQ(X)$.

The following example shows that Corollary 1 is not true in a BCI-algebra.

Example 2. Consider a BCI-algebra $(\mathbb{Z}, -, 0)$. If we take $A = \mathbb{N}$ and $B = \mathbb{Z}$, then $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(\mathbb{Z})$. However, it is not a subalgebra of $NQ(\mathbb{Z})$ since

$$(2, 3T, -5I, 6F) \odot (3, 5T, 6I, -7F) = (-1, -2T, -11I, 13F) \notin NQ(A, B)$$

for $(2, 3T, -5I, 6F), (3, 5T, 6I, -7F) \in NQ(A, B)$.

Theorem 5. If A and B are closed ideals of a BCI-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. If A and B are closed ideals of a BCI-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ by Theorem 4. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{x} = (0 * x_1, (0 * x_2)T, (0 * x_3)I, (0 * x_4)F) \in NQ(A, B)$$

since $0 * x_1, 0 * x_2 \in A$ and $0 * x_3, 0 * x_4 \in B$. Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Since every closed ideal of a BCI-algebra X is a subalgebra of X , we have the following corollary.

Corollary 2. If A and B are closed ideals of a BCI-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a subalgebra of $NQ(X)$.

In the following example, we know that there exist ideals A and B in a BCI-algebra X such that $NQ(A, B)$ is not a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Example 3. Consider BCI-algebras $(Y, *, 0)$ and $(\mathbb{Z}, -, 0)$. Then $X = Y \times \mathbb{Z}$ is a BCI-algebra (see [21]). Let $A = Y \times \mathbb{N}$ and $B = \{0\} \times \mathbb{N}$. Then A and B are ideals of X , so $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ by Theorem 4. Let $((0, 0), (0, 1)T, (0, 2)I, (0, 3)F) \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & ((0, 0), (0, 0)T, (0, 0)I, (0, 0)F) \odot ((0, 0), (0, 1)T, (0, 2)I, (0, 3)F) \\ & = ((0, 0), (0, -1)T, (0, -2)I, (0, -3)F) \notin NQ(A, B). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $NQ(A, B)$ is not a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

We provide conditions where the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Theorem 6. Let A and B be ideals of a BCI-algebra X and let

$$\Gamma := \{ \tilde{a} \in NQ(X) \mid (\forall \tilde{x} \in NQ(X)) (\tilde{x} \ll \tilde{a} \Rightarrow \tilde{x} = \tilde{a}) \}.$$

Assume that, if $\Gamma \subseteq NQ(A, B)$, then $|\Gamma| < \infty$. Then $NQ(A, B)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. If A and B are ideals of X , then $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ by Theorem 4. Let $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2T, a_3I, a_4F) \in NQ(A, B)$. For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, denote $n(\tilde{a}) := \tilde{0} \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a})^n$. Then $n(\tilde{a}) \in \Gamma$ and

$$\begin{aligned} n(\tilde{a}) & = (0 * (0 * a_1)^n, (0 * (0 * a_2)^n)T, (0 * (0 * a_3)^n)I, (0 * (0 * a_4)^n)F) \\ & = (0 * (0 * a_1^n), (0 * (0 * a_2^n))T, (0 * (0 * a_3^n))I, (0 * (0 * a_4^n))F) \\ & = \tilde{0} \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a}^n). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} n(\tilde{a}) \odot \tilde{a}^n & = (\tilde{0} \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a}^n)) \odot \tilde{a}^n \\ & = (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a}^n) \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a}^n) \\ & = \tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B), \end{aligned}$$

so $n(\tilde{a}) \in NQ(A, B)$, since $\tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)$, and $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. Since $|\Gamma| < \infty$, it follows that $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n(\tilde{a}) = (n + k)(\tilde{a})$, that is, $n(\tilde{a}) = n(\tilde{a}) \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a})^k$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned} k(\tilde{a}) &= \tilde{0} \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a})^k \\ &= (n(\tilde{a}) \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a})^k) \odot n(\tilde{a}) \\ &= n(\tilde{a}) \odot n(\tilde{a}) = \tilde{0}, \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $(k - 1)(\tilde{a}) \odot (\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a}) = \tilde{0}$. Since $\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a} \in \Gamma$, it follows that $\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a} = (k - 1)(\tilde{a}) \in NQ(A, B)$. Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 7. Given two elements a and b in a BCI-algebra X , let

$$A_a := \{x \in X \mid a * x = a\} \text{ and } B_b := \{x \in X \mid b * x = b\}. \tag{14}$$

Then $NQ(A_a, B_b)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. Since $a * 0 = a$ and $b * 0 = b$, we have $0 \in A_a \cap B_b$. Thus, $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A_a, B_b)$. If $x \in A_a$ and $y \in B_b$, then

$$0 * x = (a * x) * a = a * a = 0 \text{ and } 0 * y = (b * y) * b = b * b = 0. \tag{15}$$

Let $x, y, c, d \in X$ be such that $x, y * x \in A_a$ and $c, d * c \in B_b$. Then

$$(a * y) * a = 0 * y = (0 * y) * 0 = (0 * y) * (0 * x) = 0 * (y * x) = 0$$

and

$$(b * d) * b = 0 * d = (0 * d) * 0 = (0 * d) * (0 * c) = 0 * (d * c) = 0,$$

that is, $a * y \leq a$ and $b * d \leq b$. On the other hand,

$$a = a * (y * x) = (a * x) * (y * x) \leq a * y$$

and

$$b = b * (d * c) = (b * c) * (d * c) \leq b * d.$$

Thus, $a * y = a$ and $b * d = b$, i.e., $y \in A_a$ and $d \in B_b$. Hence, A_a and B_b are ideals of X , and $NQ(A_a, B_b)$ is therefore an ideal of $NQ(X)$ by Theorem 4. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A_a, B_b)$. Then $x_1, x_2 \in A_a$, and $x_3, x_4 \in B_b$. It follows from Equation (15) that $0 * x_1 = 0 \in A_a$, $0 * x_2 = 0 \in A_a$, $0 * x_3 = 0 \in B_b$, and $0 * x_4 = 0 \in B_b$. Hence,

$$\tilde{0} \odot \tilde{x} = (0 * x_1, (0 * x_2)T, (0 * x_3)I, (0 * x_4)F) \in NQ(A_a, B_b).$$

Therefore, $NQ(A_a, B_b)$ is a closed ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Proposition 3. Let A and B be ideals of a BCK-algebra X . Then

$$NQ(A) \cap NQ(B) = \{\tilde{0}\} \Leftrightarrow (\forall \tilde{x} \in NQ(A))(\forall \tilde{y} \in NQ(B))(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{x}). \tag{16}$$

Proof. Note that $NQ(A)$ and $NQ(B)$ are ideals of $NQ(X)$. Assume that $NQ(A) \cap NQ(B) = \{\tilde{0}\}$. Let

$$\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A) \text{ and } \tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F) \in NQ(B).$$

Since $\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \ll \tilde{x}$ and $\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \ll \tilde{y}$, it follows that $\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \in NQ(A) \cap NQ(B) = \{\tilde{0}\}$. Obviously, $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{x} \in \{\tilde{0}\}$. Hence, $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{x}$.

Conversely, suppose that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{x}$ for all $\tilde{x} \in NQ(A)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(B)$. If $\tilde{z} \in NQ(A) \cap NQ(B)$, then $\tilde{z} \in NQ(A)$ and $\tilde{z} \in NQ(B)$, which is implied from the hypothesis that $\tilde{z} = \tilde{z} \odot \tilde{z} = \tilde{0}$. Hence $NQ(A) \cap NQ(B) = \{\tilde{0}\}$. \square

Theorem 8. Let A and B be subsets of a BCK-algebra X such that

$$(\forall a, b \in A \cap B)(K(a, b) \subseteq A \cap B) \tag{17}$$

where $K(a, b) := \{x \in X \mid x * a \leq b\}$. Then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. If $x \in A \cap B$, then $0 \in K(x, x)$ since $0 * x \leq x$. Hence, $0 \in A \cap B$ by Equation (17), so it is clear that $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$ and $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $x_1 * y_1 \in A$, $x_2 * y_2 \in A$, $x_3 * y_3 \in B$, and $x_4 * y_4 \in B$. Using (II), we have $x_1 \in K(x_1 * y_1, y_1) \subseteq A$, $x_2 \in K(x_2 * y_2, y_2) \subseteq A$, $x_3 \in K(x_3 * y_3, y_3) \subseteq B$, and $x_4 \in K(x_4 * y_4, y_4) \subseteq B$. This implies that $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A, B)$. Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Corollary 3. Let A and B be subsets of a BCK-algebra X such that

$$(\forall a, x, y \in X)(x, y \in A \cap B, (a * x) * y = 0 \Rightarrow a \in A \cap B). \tag{18}$$

Then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Theorem 9. Let A and B be nonempty subsets of a BCK-algebra X such that

$$(\forall a, x, y \in X)(x, y \in A \text{ (or } B), a * x \leq y \Rightarrow a \in A \text{ (or } B)). \tag{19}$$

Then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. Assume that the condition expressed by Equation (19) is valid for nonempty subsets A and B of X . Since $0 * x \leq x$ for any $x \in A$ (or B), we have $0 \in A$ (or B) by Equation (19). Hence, it is clear that $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$ and $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} = (x_1 * y_1, (x_2 * y_2)T, (x_3 * y_3)I, (x_4 * y_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $x_1 * y_1 \in A$, $x_2 * y_2 \in A$, $x_3 * y_3 \in B$, and $x_4 * y_4 \in B$. Note that $x_i * (x_i * y_i) \leq y_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. It follows from Equation (19) that $x_1, x_2 \in A$ and $x_3, x_4 \in B$. Hence,

$$\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F) \in NQ(A, B);$$

therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 10. If A and B are positive implicative ideals of a BCK-algebra X , then the set $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$, which is called a positive implicative neutrosophic quadruple ideal.

Proof. Assume that A and B are positive implicative ideals of a BCK-algebra X . Obviously, $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$, $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$, and $\tilde{z} = (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} = ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1, ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)T, ((x_3 * y_3) * z_3)I, ((x_4 * y_4) * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

and

$$\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} = (y_1 * z_1, (y_2 * z_2)T, (y_3 * z_3)I, (y_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $(x_1 * y_1) * z_1 \in A$, $(x_2 * y_2) * z_2 \in A$, $(x_3 * y_3) * z_3 \in B$, $(x_4 * y_4) * z_4 \in B$, $y_1 * z_1 \in A$, $y_2 * z_2 \in A$, $y_3 * z_3 \in B$, and $y_4 * z_4 \in B$. Since A and B are positive implicative ideals of X , it follows that $x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2 \in A$ and $x_3 * z_3, x_4 * z_4 \in B$. Hence,

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} = (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 11. Let A and B be ideals of a BCK-algebra X such that

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x * y) * z \in A \text{ (or } B) \Rightarrow (x * z) * (y * z) \in A \text{ (or } B)). \tag{20}$$

Then $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. Since A and B are ideals of X , it follows from Theorem 4 that $NQ(A, B)$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$, $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$, and $\tilde{z} = (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} = ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1, ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)T, ((x_3 * y_3) * z_3)I, ((x_4 * y_4) * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

and

$$\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} = (y_1 * z_1, (y_2 * z_2)T, (y_3 * z_3)I, (y_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $(x_1 * y_1) * z_1 \in A$, $(x_2 * y_2) * z_2 \in A$, $(x_3 * y_3) * z_3 \in B$, $(x_4 * y_4) * z_4 \in B$, $y_1 * z_1 \in A$, $y_2 * z_2 \in A$, $y_3 * z_3 \in B$, and $y_4 * z_4 \in B$. It follows from Equation (20) that $(x_1 * z_1) * (y_1 * z_1) \in A$, $(x_2 * z_2) * (y_2 * z_2) \in A$, $(x_3 * z_3) * (y_3 * z_3) \in B$, and $(x_4 * z_4) * (y_4 * z_4) \in B$. Since A and B are ideals of X , we get $x_1 * z_1 \in A$, $x_2 * z_2 \in A$, $x_3 * z_3 \in B$, and $x_4 * z_4 \in B$. Hence,

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} = (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B).$$

Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Corollary 4. Let A and B be ideals of a BCK-algebra X such that

$$(\forall x, y \in X)((x * y) * y \in A \text{ (or } B) \Rightarrow x * y \in A \text{ (or } B)). \tag{21}$$

Then $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. If the condition expressed in Equation (21) is valid, then the condition expressed in Equation (20) is true. Hence, $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$ by Theorem 11. \square

Theorem 12. Let A and B be subsets of a BCK-algebra X such that $0 \in A \cap B$ and

$$((x * y) * y) * z \in A \text{ (or } B), z \in A \text{ (or } B) \Rightarrow x * y \in A \text{ (or } B) \tag{22}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. Then $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. Since $0 \in A \cap B$, it is clear that $\tilde{0} \in NQ(A, B)$. We first show that

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(x * y \in A \text{ (or } B), y \in A \text{ (or } B) \Rightarrow x \in A \text{ (or } B)). \tag{23}$$

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x * y \in A \text{ (or } B)$ and $y \in A \text{ (or } B)$. Then

$$((x * 0) * 0) * y = x * y \in A \text{ (or } B)$$

by Equation (1), which, based on Equations (1) and (22), implies that $x = x * 0 \in A \text{ (or } B)$. Let $\tilde{x} = (x_1, x_2T, x_3I, x_4F)$, $\tilde{y} = (y_1, y_2T, y_3I, y_4F)$, and $\tilde{z} = (z_1, z_2T, z_3I, z_4F)$ be elements of $NQ(X)$ such that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} &= ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1, ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)T, \\ &((x_3 * y_3) * z_3)I, ((x_4 * y_4) * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} = (y_1 * z_1, (y_2 * z_2)T, (y_3 * z_3)I, (y_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B),$$

so $(x_1 * y_1) * z_1 \in A$, $(x_2 * y_2) * z_2 \in A$, $(x_3 * y_3) * z_3 \in B$, $(x_4 * y_4) * z_4 \in B$, $y_1 * z_1 \in A$, $y_2 * z_2 \in A$, $y_3 * z_3 \in B$, and $y_4 * z_4 \in B$. Note that

$$(((x_i * z_i) * z_i) * (y_i * z_i)) * ((x_i * y_i) * z_i) = 0 \in A \text{ (or } B)$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Since $(x_i * y_i) * z_i \in A$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $(x_j * y_j) * z_j \in B$ for $j = 3, 4$, it follows from Equation (23) that $((x_i * z_i) * z_i) * (y_i * z_i) \in A$ for $i = 1, 2$, and $((x_j * z_j) * z_j) * (y_j * z_j) \in B$ for $j = 3, 4$. Moreover, since $y_i * z_i \in A$ for $i = 1, 2$, and $y_j * z_j \in B$ for $j = 3, 4$, we have $x_1 * z_1 \in A$, $x_2 * z_2 \in A$, $x_3 * z_3 \in B$, and $x_4 * z_4 \in B$ by Equation (22). Hence,

$$\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} = (x_1 * z_1, (x_2 * z_2)T, (x_3 * z_3)I, (x_4 * z_4)F) \in NQ(A, B).$$

Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 13. Let A and B be subsets of a BCK-algebra X such that $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. Then the set

$$\Omega_{\tilde{a}} := \{\tilde{x} \in NQ(X) \mid \tilde{x} \odot \tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)\} \tag{24}$$

is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ for any $\tilde{a} \in NQ(X)$.

Proof. Obviously, $\tilde{0} \in \Omega_{\tilde{a}}$. Let $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(X)$ be such that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{a}}$ and $\tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{a}}$. Then $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)$. Since $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$, it follows from Equation (11) that $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)$ and therefore that $\tilde{x} \in \Omega_{\tilde{a}}$. Hence, $\Omega_{\tilde{a}}$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Combining Theorems 12 and 13, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 5. *If A and B are subsets of a BCK-algebra X satisfying $0 \in A \cap B$ and the condition expressed in Equation (22), then the set $\Omega_{\tilde{a}}$ in Equation (24) is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ for all $\tilde{a} \in NQ(X)$.*

Theorem 14. *For any subsets A and B of a BCK-algebra X , if the set $\Omega_{\tilde{a}}$ in Equation (24) is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ for all $\tilde{a} \in NQ(X)$, then $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.*

Proof. Since $\tilde{0} \in \Omega_{\tilde{a}}$, we have $\tilde{0} = \tilde{0} \odot \tilde{a} \in NQ(A, B)$. Let $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)$ be such that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$. Then $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$ and $\tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$. Since $\Omega_{\tilde{z}}$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$, it follows that $\tilde{x} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$. Hence, $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} \in NQ(A, B)$. Therefore, $NQ(A, B)$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

Theorem 15. *For any ideals A and B of a BCK-algebra X and for any $\tilde{a} \in NQ(X)$, if the set $\Omega_{\tilde{a}}$ in Equation (24) is an ideal of $NQ(X)$, then $NQ(X)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra.*

Proof. Let Ω be any ideal of $NQ(X)$. For any $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in NQ(X)$, assume that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z} \in \Omega$. Then $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$ and $\tilde{y} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$. Since $\Omega_{\tilde{z}}$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$, it follows that $\tilde{x} \in \Omega_{\tilde{z}}$. Hence, $\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z} \in \Omega$, which shows that Ω is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. Therefore, $NQ(X)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra. \square

In general, the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is an ideal of any neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra $NQ(X)$, but it is not a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$ as seen in the following example.

Example 4. *Consider a BCK-algebra $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ with the binary operation $*$, which is given in Table 3.*

Table 3. Cayley table for the binary operation “ $*$ ”.

$*$	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	1	0

Then the neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra $NQ(X)$ has 81 elements. If we take $\tilde{a} = (2, 2T, 2I, 2F)$ and $\tilde{b} = (1, 1T, 1I, 1F)$ in $NQ(X)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\tilde{a} \odot \tilde{b}) \odot \tilde{b} &= ((2 * 1) * 1, ((2 * 1) * 1)T, ((2 * 1) * 1)I, ((2 * 1) * 1)F) \\
 &= (1 * 1, (1 * 1)T, (1 * 1)I, (1 * 1)F) = (0, 0T, 0I, 0F) = \tilde{0},
 \end{aligned}$$

and $\tilde{b} \odot \tilde{b} = \tilde{0}$. However,

$$\tilde{a} \odot \tilde{b} = (2 * 1, (2 * 1)T, (2 * 1)I, (2 * 1)F) = (1, 1T, 1I, 1F) \neq \tilde{0}.$$

Hence, $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is not a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.

We now provide conditions for the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ to be a positive implicative ideal in the neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra.

Theorem 16. *Let $NQ(X)$ be a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra. If the set*

$$\Omega(\tilde{a}) := \{\tilde{x} \in NQ(X) \mid \tilde{x} \ll \tilde{a}\} \tag{25}$$

is an ideal of $NQ(X)$ for all $\tilde{a} \in NQ(X)$, then $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$.

Proof. We first show that

$$(\forall \tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(X))((\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{0} \Rightarrow \tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}). \tag{26}$$

Assume that $(\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}$ for all $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in NQ(X)$. Then $\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{y}$, so $\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y} \in \Omega(\tilde{y})$. Since $\tilde{y} \in \Omega(\tilde{y})$ and $\Omega(\tilde{y})$ is an ideal of $NQ(X)$, we have $\tilde{x} \in \Omega(\tilde{y})$. Thus, $\tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y}$, that is, $\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}$. Let $\tilde{u} := (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y}$. Then

$$((\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{u}) \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y} = ((\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{u} = \tilde{0},$$

which implies, based on Equations (3) and (26), that

$$(\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ ((\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y}) = (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{u} = (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{u}) \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{0},$$

that is, $\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y} \ll (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y}$. Since $(\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y} \ll \tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}$, it follows that

$$(\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \circ \tilde{y} = \tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}. \tag{27}$$

If we put $\tilde{y} = \tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))$ in Equation (27), then

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) &= (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})))) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) \\ &\ll (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) \\ &\ll (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y}) \\ &= (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \\ &= ((\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \\ &\ll (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} &((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})))) \\ &= ((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})))) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \\ &= ((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \\ &\ll (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) = \tilde{0}, \end{aligned}$$

so $((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})))) = \tilde{0}$, that is,

$$((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \ll \tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))).$$

Hence,

$$\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}))) = ((\tilde{x} \circ (\tilde{x} \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})). \tag{28}$$

If we use $\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}$ instead of \tilde{x} in Equation (28), then

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x} &= (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ \tilde{0} \\ &= (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ ((\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})))) \\ &= ((\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ ((\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ \tilde{y})) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})) \\ &= (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x}) \circ (\tilde{y} \circ (\tilde{y} \circ \tilde{x})), \end{aligned}$$

which, by taking $\tilde{x} = \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}$, implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) &= (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}))) \\ &= (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}). \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) &= ((\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \\ &\ll (\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \\ &= (\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y})) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}), \end{aligned}$$

so,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x} &= (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}))) \odot \tilde{0} \\ &= (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}))) \odot ((\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot \tilde{y}) \\ &\ll ((\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot ((\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot \tilde{y})) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \\ &= (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x})) \\ &\ll (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot \tilde{x}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot \tilde{x} \ll \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}$, it follows that

$$(\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}) \odot \tilde{x} = \tilde{y} \odot \tilde{x}. \tag{29}$$

Based on Equation (29), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} &((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) * (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})) \odot ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}) \\ &= (((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})) \odot ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}) \\ &\ll ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot \tilde{y}) \odot ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}) \\ &= \tilde{0}, \end{aligned}$$

that is, $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) * (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z}) \ll (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} &((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}) \odot ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})) \\ &= ((\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z}) \odot ((\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})) \odot \tilde{z}) \\ &\ll (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot (\tilde{x} \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})) \\ &\ll (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot \tilde{y} = \tilde{0}, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} \ll (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})$. Hence, $(\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{y}) \odot \tilde{z} = (\tilde{x} \odot \tilde{z}) \odot (\tilde{y} \odot \tilde{z})$. Therefore, $NQ(X)$ is a positive implicative, so $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is a positive implicative ideal of $NQ(X)$. \square

4. Conclusions

We have considered a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number on a set and established neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebras, which consist of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-numbers. We have investigated several properties and considered ideal theory in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra and a closed ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra. Using subsets A and B of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra, we have considered sets $NQ(A, B)$, which consist of neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-numbers with a condition. We have provided conditions for the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (positive implicative) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra, and the set $NQ(A, B)$ to be a (closed) ideal of a neutrosophic quadruple BCI-algebra. We have provided an example

to show that the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ is not a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra, and we have considered conditions for the set $\{\tilde{0}\}$ to be a positive implicative ideal in a neutrosophic quadruple BCK-algebra.

Author Contributions: Y.B.J. and S.-Z.S. initiated the main idea of this work and wrote the paper. F.S. and H.B. provided examples and checked the content. All authors conceived and designed the new definitions and results, and have read and approved the final manuscript for submission.

Acknowledgments: The authors wish to thank the anonymous reviewers for their valuable suggestions. The second author, Seok-Zun Song, was supported under the framework of international cooperation program managed by the National Research Foundation of Korea (2017K2A9A1A01092970).

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Smarandache, F. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic, ProQuest Information & Learning, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA, p. 105, 1998. Available online: <http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/eBook-neutrosophics6.pdf> (accessed on 1 September 2007).
2. Smarandache, F. *A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability*; American Reserch Press: Rehoboth, NM, USA, 1999.
3. Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic set—A generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy set. *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math.* **2005**, *24*, 287–297.
4. Garg, H. Linguistic single-valued neutrosophic prioritized aggregation operators and their applications to multiple-attribute group decision-making. *J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput.* **2018**, in press. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Garg, H. Non-linear programming method for multi-criteria decision making problems under interval neutrosophic set environment. *Appl. Intell.* **2017**, in press. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Garg, H. Some New Biparametric Distance Measures on Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets with Applications to Pattern Recognition and Medical Diagnosis. *Information* **2017**, *8*, 162. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Garg, H. Novel single-valued neutrosophic aggregated operators under Frank norm operation and its application to decision-making process. *Int. J. Uncertain. Quantif.* **2016**, *6*, 361–375.
8. Garg, H.; Garg, N. On single-valued neutrosophic entropy of order α . *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* **2016**, *14*, 21–28.
9. Saeid, A.B.; Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic subalgebras of BCK/BCI-algebras based on neutrosophic points. *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **2017**, *14*, 87–97.
10. Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic subalgebras of several types in BCK/BCI-algebras. *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **2017**, *14*, 75–86.
11. Jun, Y.B.; Kim, S.J.; Smarandache, F. Interval neutrosophic sets with applications in BCK/BCI-algebra. *Axioms* **2018**, *7*, 23. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Jun, Y.B.; Smarandache, F.; Bordbar, H. Neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -structures applied to BCK/BCI-algebras. *Information* **2017**, *8*, 128. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Jun, Y.B.; Smarandache, F.; Song, S.Z.; Khan, M. Neutrosophic positive implicative \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras. *Axioms* **2018**, *7*, 3. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Khan, M.; Anis, S.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -structures and their applications in semigroups. *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **2017**, *14*, 583–598.
15. Öztürk, M.A.; Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras based on neutrosophic points. *J. Inter. Math. Virtual Inst.* **2018**, *8*, 1–17.
16. Song, S.Z.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic commutative \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK-algebras. *Information* **2017**, *8*, 130. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Agboola, A.A.A.; Davvaz, B.; Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic quadruple algebraic hyperstructures. *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* **2017**, *14*, 29–42.
18. Akinleye, S.A.; Smarandache, F.; Agboola, A.A.A. On neutrosophic quadruple algebraic structures. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* **2016**, *12*, 122–126.
19. Iséki, K. On BCI-algebras. *Math. Semin. Notes* **1980**, *8*, 125–130.

20. Iséki, K.; Tanaka, S. An introduction to the theory of *BCK*-algebras. *Math. Jpn.* **1978**, *23*, 1–26.
21. Huang, Y. *BCI-Algebra*; Science Press: Beijing, China, 2006.
22. Meng, J.; Jun, Y.B. *BCK-Algebras*; Kyungmoonsa Co.: Seoul, Korea, 1994.

© 2018 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).